

Fuzzy I_{rw} -Continuous Functions in The Sense of Šostak's

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Abstract

In this paper we introduce the concept of r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set and r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open sets in fuzzy ideal topological spaces in the sense of Šostak's. Also, fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous and fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute mappings are introduced and studied and obtain some of its basic properties and characterizations. Several examples are given to illustrate the concepts.

Keywords: r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed sets, r -fuzzy I_{rw} - $T_{1/2}$ space, fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous, fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute.

1. Introduction

In 1945 R. Vaidyanathaswamy [24] introduced the concept of ideal topological spaces. Hayashi [4] defined the local function and studied some topological properties using local function in ideal topological spaces in 1964. Since then many mathematicians studied various topological concepts in ideal topological spaces. After the introduction of fuzzy sets by Zadeh [25] in 1965 and fuzzy topology by Chang [1] in 1968, several researches were conducted on the generalization of the notions of fuzzy sets and fuzzy topology. The hybridization of fuzzy topology and fuzzy ideal theory was initiated by Mahmoud [12] and Sarkar [16] independently in 1997. They ([12], [16]) introduced the concept of fuzzy ideal topological spaces as an extension of fuzzy topological spaces and ideal topological spaces.

Šostak [18] introduced the fundamental concept of a fuzzy topological structure, as an extension of both crisp topology and fuzzy topology [1], in the sense that not only the objects are fuzzified, but also the axiomatics. In [19, 20], Šostak gave some rules and showed how such an extension can be realized. Chattopadhyay et al., [3] have redefined the same concept under the name gradation of openness. A general approach to the study of topological type structures on fuzzy power sets was developed in [5, 6, 7, 10, 11]. Recently, Taha [22]

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introduced the concept of r -fuzzy \mathcal{I} -open, r -fuzzy semi- \mathcal{I} -open, r -fuzzy α - \mathcal{I} -open, r -fuzzy β - \mathcal{I} -open in fuzzy ideal topological spaces in the sense of Šostak. In this paper we introduce the concept of fuzzy I_{rw} -closed sets, fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous and fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute mappings in fuzzy ideal topological spaces in the sense of Šostak's and obtain some of its basic properties and characterizations.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, let X be a nonempty set, $I = [0, 1]$ and $I_0 = (0, 1]$. For $\lambda \in I$, $\bar{\lambda}(x) = \lambda$ for all $x \in X$. The family of all fuzzy sets on X denoted by I^X . For $x \in X$ and $t \in I_0$, a fuzzy point x_t is defined by

$$x_t(y) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x. \end{cases}$$

Let $Pt(X)$ be the family of all fuzzy points in X . A fuzzy point $x_t \in \lambda$ iff $t < \lambda(x)$. A fuzzy set λ is quasi-coincident with μ denoted by $\lambda q \mu$, if there exists $x \in X$ such that $\lambda(x)q\mu(x) > 1$. If λ is not quasi-coincident with μ , we denote $\lambda \bar{q} \mu$.

Lemma 2.1. [8] Let X be a nonempty set and $\lambda, \mu \in I^X$. Then:

- (1) $\lambda q \mu$ iff there exists $x_t \in \lambda$ such that $x_t q \mu$.
- (2) If $\lambda q \mu$, then $\lambda \wedge \mu \neq \bar{0}$.
- (3) $\lambda \bar{q} \mu$ iff $\lambda \leq \bar{1} - \mu$.
- (4) $\lambda \leq \mu$ iff $x_t \in \lambda$ implies $x_t \in \mu$ iff $x_t q \lambda$ implies $x_t q \mu$ implies $x_t \bar{q} \lambda$.
- (5) $x_t \bar{q} \bigvee_{i \in \Gamma} \mu_i$ iff there exists $i_0 \in \Gamma$ such that $x_t \bar{q} \mu_{i_0}$.

Definition 2.2. [18] A function $\tau : I^X \rightarrow I$ is called a fuzzy topology on X if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (O1) $\tau(\bar{0}) = \tau(\bar{1}) = 1$,
- (O2) $\tau(\bigvee_{i \in \Gamma} \mu_i) \geq \bigwedge_{i \in \Gamma} \tau(\mu_i)$, for any $\{\mu_i\}_{i \in \Gamma} \subset I^X$,
- (O3) $\tau(\mu_1 \wedge \mu_2) \geq \tau(\mu_1) \wedge \tau(\mu_2)$, for any $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in I^X$.

The pair (X, τ) is called a fuzzy topological space (for short, fts).

Theorem 2.3. [2] Let (X, τ) be a fts. Then for each $\lambda \in I^X$ and $r \in I_0$, we define an operator $C_\tau : I^X \times I_0 \rightarrow I^X$ as follows: $C_\tau(\lambda, r) = \bigwedge \{\mu \in I^X : \lambda \leq \mu, \tau(\bar{1} - \mu) \geq r\}$. For $\lambda, \mu \in I^X$ and $r, s \in I_0$, the operator C_τ satisfies the following statements:

- (C1) $C_\tau(\bar{0}, r) = \bar{0}$,
- (C2) $\lambda \leq C_\tau(\lambda, r)$,
- (C3) $C_\tau(\lambda, r) \vee C_\tau(\mu, r) = C_\tau(\lambda \vee \mu, r)$,
- (C4) $C_\tau(\lambda, r) \leq C_\tau(\lambda, s)$ if $r \leq s$,
- (C5) $C_\tau(C_\tau(\lambda, r), r) = C_\tau(\lambda, r)$.

The fuzzy closure operator C_τ generates a fuzzy topology $\tau_{C_\tau}(\lambda) : I^X \rightarrow I$ given by

- (C6) $\tau_{C_\tau}(\lambda) = \bigvee \{r \in I \mid C_\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda, r) = \bar{1} - \lambda\}$.

Theorem 2.4. [2] Let (X, τ) be a fts. Then for each $\lambda \in I^X$ and $r \in I_0$, we define an operator $I_\tau : I^X \times I_0 \rightarrow I^X$ as follows: $I_\tau(\lambda, r) = \bigvee \{\mu \in I^X : \mu \leq \lambda, \tau(\mu) \geq r\}$. For $\lambda, \mu \in I^X$ and $r, s \in I_0$, the operator I_τ satisfies the following statements:

- (I1) $I_\tau(\bar{1}, r) = \bar{1}$,
- (I2) $I_\tau(\lambda, r) \leq \lambda$,

- (I3) $I_\tau(\lambda, r) \wedge I_\tau(\mu, r) = I_\tau(\lambda \wedge \mu, r)$,
- (I4) $I_\tau(\lambda, r) \leq I_\tau(\lambda, s)$ if $s \leq r$,
- (I5) $I_\tau(I_\tau(\lambda, r), r) = I_\tau(\lambda, r)$.
- (I6) $I_\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda, r) = \bar{1} - C_\tau(\lambda, r)$ and $C_\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda, r) = \bar{1} - I_\tau(\lambda, r)$

The fuzzy interior operator I_τ generates a fuzzy topology $\tau_{I_\tau}(\lambda) : I^X \rightarrow I$ given by

(I7) $\tau_{I_\tau}(\lambda) = \bigvee \{r \in I \mid I_\tau(\lambda, r) = \lambda\}$.

Definition 2.5. Let (X, τ) be a smooth topological space, $\lambda \in I^X$ and $r \in I_0$. Then λ is called:

- (1) r -fuzzy regular open (for short, r -fro) [17] if $\lambda = I_\tau(C_\tau(\lambda, r), r)$.
- (2) r -fuzzy regular closed (for short, r -frc) [17] if $\lambda = C_\tau(I_\tau(\lambda, r), r)$.
- (3) r -fuzzy semi open (for short, r -fso) [15] if there exists $\mu \in I^X$ with $\tau(\mu) \geq r$ and $\mu \leq \lambda \leq C_\tau(\mu, r)$.
- (4) r -fuzzy semi closed (for short, r -fsc) [15] if there exists $\mu \in I^X$ with $\tau(\bar{1} - \mu) \geq r$ and $I_\tau(\mu, r) \leq \lambda \leq \mu$.
- (5) r -fuzzy regular semi open (for short, r -frso) [23] if there exists r -fro set $\mu \in I^X$ and $\mu \leq \lambda \leq C_\tau(\mu, r)$.
- (6) r -fuzzy regular semi closed (for short, r -frsc) [23] if there exists r -frc set $\mu \in I^X$ and $I_\tau(\mu, r) \leq \lambda \leq \mu$.

Definition 2.6. [14] A mapping $\mathcal{I} : I^X \rightarrow I$ is called fuzzy ideal on X iff

- (1) if $\lambda \leq \mu$, then $\mathcal{I}(\lambda) \leq \mathcal{I}(\mu)$, for each $\lambda, \mu \in I^X$.
- (2) For each $\lambda, \mu \in I^X$, $\mathcal{I}(\lambda \vee \mu) \geq \mathcal{I}(\lambda) \wedge \mathcal{I}(\mu)$.

Also, \mathcal{I} is called proper if $\mathcal{I}(\bar{1}) = 0$ and there exists $\mu \in I^X$ such that $\mathcal{I}(\mu) > 0$. The simplest fuzzy ideals on X are $\mathcal{I}_0 = \{0_X\}$ and $\mathcal{I}_1 = \{I^X\}$ are defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{I}_0(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda = \bar{0} \\ 0 & \text{if otherwise.} \end{cases} \text{ and } \mathcal{I}_1(\lambda) = 1, \text{ for all } \lambda \in I^X.$$

Definition 2.7. [21] Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fuzzy ideal topological space. Let $\lambda \in I^X$, The r -fuzzy local function λ_r^* of λ is defined as follows: $\lambda_r^* = \bigwedge \{\mu \in I^X : \mathcal{I}(\lambda \bar{\vee} \mu) \geq r, \tau(1 - \mu) \geq r\}$.

If we take $\mathcal{I} = 0_X$, for each $\lambda \in I^X$ we have $\lambda_r^* = C_\tau(\lambda, r)$. Also, if we take $\mathcal{I} = I^X$, for each $\lambda \in I^X$ we have $\lambda_r^* = \bar{0}$. Moreover, we define an operator $C_\tau^* : I^X \times I_0 \rightarrow I^X$ as follows:

$$C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) = \lambda \vee \lambda_r^*.$$

For $\lambda, \mu \in I^X$, the operator C_τ^* satisfies the following conditions:

- (1) If $\lambda \leq \mu$, then $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq C_\tau^*(\mu, r)$.
- (2) $C_\tau^*(C_\tau^*(\lambda, r), r) = C_\tau^*(\lambda, r)$.
- (3) $C_\tau^*(\lambda \vee \mu, r) = C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \vee C_\tau^*(\mu, r)$.
- (4) $C_\tau^*(\lambda \wedge \mu, r) \leq C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \wedge C_\tau^*(\mu, r)$.

Lemma 2.8. [13] $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \Leftrightarrow (\lambda_1 q(1 - \lambda_2))$ for every pair of fuzzy sets $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in I^X$.

Definition 2.9. [9] Let (X, τ) and (Y, η) be a fts's. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \eta)$ be a function. Then f is called:

- (1) fuzzy continuous (F-continuous) iff $\eta(\mu) \leq \tau(f^{-1}(\mu))$ for each $\mu \in I^Y$.
- (2) fuzzy open (F-open) iff $\tau(\lambda) \leq \eta(f(\lambda))$ for each $\lambda \in I^X$.
- (3) fuzzy closed (F-closed) iff $\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda) \leq \eta(\bar{1} - f(\lambda))$ for each $\lambda \in I^X$.

3. r -Fuzzy I_{rw} -closed sets

Definition 3.1. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be fits. A fuzzy set $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$ is called

- (1) r -fuzzy rw -closed if $C_\tau(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$, whenever $\lambda \leq \mu$ and μ is r -frso.
- (2) r -fuzzy I_w -closed if $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$, whenever $\lambda \leq \mu$ and μ is r -fso.
- (3) r -fuzzy I_{rg} -closed if $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$, whenever $\lambda \leq \mu$ and μ is r -fro.
- (4) r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed if $\lambda^* \leq \mu$, whenever $\lambda \leq \mu$ and μ is r -frso.

A fuzzy set λ is called r -fuzzy rw -Closed (resp. r -fuzzy I_w -Closed, r -fuzzy I_{rg} -Closed, r -fuzzy I_{rw} -Closed) if its complement $\bar{1} - \lambda$ is r -fuzzy rw -open (resp. r -fuzzy I_w -open, r -fuzzy I_{rg} -open, r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open).

Remark 3.2. (i) Every r -fuzzy rw -closed set is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed, but the converse is not true.

(ii) Every r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set is r -fuzzy I_{rg} -closed, but the converse is not true.

(iii) Every r -fuzzy I_w -closed set is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed, but the converse is not true.

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \lambda \in I^X$ are defined as follows: $\alpha(a) = 0.5, \alpha(b) = 0.4, \alpha(c) = 0.6, \alpha(d) = 0.4; \beta(a) = 0.4, \beta(b) = 0.6, \beta(c) = 0.4, \beta(d) = 0.5; \gamma(a) = 0.5, \gamma(b) = 0.6, \gamma(c) = 0.6, \gamma(d) = 0.5; \delta(a) = 0.4, \delta(b) = 0.4, \delta(c) = 0.4, \delta(d) = 0.4; \lambda(a) = 0.5, \lambda(b) = 0.4, \lambda(c) = 0.6, \lambda(d) = 0.5$. We define fuzzy ideal topology $\tau : I^X \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \alpha, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \beta, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \gamma, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \delta, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

If we take $\mathcal{I} = I^X$, then the fuzzy set λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed but it is not r -fuzzy rw -closed. Since λ is a r -frso set containing λ^* , but λ does not contain $C_\tau(\lambda, r)$ which is $\bar{1} - \beta$. Therefore λ is not r -fuzzy rw -closed set.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \lambda \in I^X$ are defined as follows: $\alpha(a) = 0.4, \alpha(b) = 0.3, \alpha(c) = 0.5, \alpha(d) = 0.3; \beta(a) = 0.3, \beta(b) = 0.5, \beta(c) = 0.3, \beta(d) = 0.4; \gamma(a) = 0.4, \gamma(b) = 0.5, \gamma(c) = 0.5, \gamma(d) = 0.4; \delta(a) = 0.3, \delta(b) = 0.3, \delta(c) = 0.3, \delta(d) = 0.3; \lambda(a) = 0.6, \lambda(b) = 0.5, \lambda(c) = 0.5, \lambda(d) = 0.5$. We define fuzzy ideal topology $\tau : I^X \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \alpha, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \beta, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \gamma, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \delta, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

If we take $\mathcal{I} = \{0_X\}$, then the fuzzy set λ is r -fuzzy I_{rg} -closed but it is not r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed. Here $\bar{1}$ is a r -frso set containing $C_\tau^*(\lambda)$. Since λ is a r -frso set, but λ does not contain λ^* which is $\bar{1} - \gamma$. Therefore λ is not r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set.

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b\}, \lambda, \mu, \gamma \in I^X$ are defined as follows: $\lambda(a) = 0.7, \lambda(b) = 0.6; \mu(a) = 0.6, \mu(b) = 0.7; \gamma(a) = 0.7, \gamma(b) = 0.7$. We define fuzzy topology $\tau : I^X \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \lambda, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

If we take $\mathcal{I} = \{0\}$, then the fuzzy set μ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed but it is not r -fuzzy I_w -closed. Since γ is a r -fso set containing μ , but γ does not contain $C_\tau^*(\mu)$ which is $\bar{1}$. Therefore μ is not r -fuzzy I_w -closed set.

For the relationship related to several sets defined above, we have the following diagram:

Diagram - I

Theorem 3.6. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $r \in I_0$. Then λ^* is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed for every $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$.

PROOF. Let $\lambda \in I^X$ and let $\mu \in I^X$ be any r -frso set such that $\lambda^* \leq \mu$. Since $(\lambda^*)^* \leq \lambda^*$ it follows that $(\lambda^*)^* \leq \mu$. Hence λ^* is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

Definition 3.7. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $r \in I_0$. A fuzzy set $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$ is called r -fuzzy $*$ -closed (resp. fuzzy $*$ -dense in itself) if $\lambda^* \leq \lambda$ (resp. $\lambda \leq \lambda^*$).

Theorem 3.8. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $r \in I_0$ and $\lambda \in I^X$ be a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed and r -frso set in X . Then λ is r -fuzzy $*$ -closed.

PROOF. Since λ is r -frso and r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed and $\lambda \leq \lambda$. It follows that $\lambda^* \leq \lambda$ because λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed. Hence $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) = \lambda \vee \lambda^* \leq \lambda$ and λ is r -fuzzy $*$ -closed.

Theorem 3.9. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits and $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$. Then the following are equivalent:

- (i) λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.
- (ii) $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$ whenever $\lambda \leq \mu$ and μ is r -frso in X .
- (iii) $\lceil(\lambda q \delta) \Rightarrow \lceil(C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) q \delta)$ for every r -frsc set $\delta \in I^X, r \in I_0$.
- (iv) $\lceil(\lambda q \delta) \Rightarrow \lceil(\lambda^* q \delta)$ for every r -frsc set $\delta \in I^X, r \in I_0$.

PROOF. (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Let λ be a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set in X . Let $\lambda \leq \mu$ where μ is r -frso set in X . Then $\lambda^* \leq \mu$. Hence $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) = \lambda \vee \lambda^* \leq \mu$. Which implies that $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i): Let $\lambda \in I^X$. By hypothesis $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$. Which implies that $\lambda^* \leq \mu$. Hence λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii): Let δ be a r -frsc set and $\lceil(\lambda q \delta)$. Then $\bar{1} - \delta$ is r -frso in X and by Lemma 2.8, $\lambda \leq \bar{1} - \delta$. Therefore, $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \bar{1} - \delta$, because λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed. Hence by Lemma 2.8, $\lceil(C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) q \delta)$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (ii): Let μ be a r -frso set of X such that $\lambda \leq \mu$. Then by Lemma 2.8, $\lceil(\lambda q (\bar{1} - \mu))$ and $\bar{1} - \mu$ is r -frsc in X . Therefore by hypothesis $\lceil(C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) q (\bar{1} - \mu))$. Hence $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$.

(i) \Rightarrow (iv): Let δ be a r -frsc set in X such that $\lceil(\lambda q \delta)$. Then $\lambda \leq \bar{1} - \delta$ where $\bar{1} - \delta$ is r -frso. Therefore by (i) $\lambda^* \leq \bar{1} - \delta$. Hence $\lceil(\lambda^* q \delta)$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i): Let δ be a r -frsc set in X such that $\lambda \leq \delta$. Then by Lemma 2.8, $\lceil(\lambda q (\bar{1} - \delta))$ and $\bar{1} - \delta$ is r -frsc in X . Therefore by hypothesis $\lceil(\lambda^* q (\bar{1} - \delta))$. Hence $\lambda^* \leq \delta$ and λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set in X .

Theorem 3.10. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits and $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$ be a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set. Then $x_\alpha q C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \Rightarrow C_\tau(x_\alpha, r)q\lambda$ for any fuzzy point x_α of X .

PROOF. Let $x_\alpha q C_\tau^*(\lambda, r)$. To prove $C_\tau(x_\alpha, r)q\lambda$. Suppose we assume that $\lceil C_\tau(x_\alpha, r)q\lambda$. We prove the result by $\lceil x_\alpha q C_\tau^*(\lambda, r)$. By assumption $\lceil C_\tau(x_\alpha, r)q\lambda$, then by Lemma 2.8, it follows that $\lambda \leq (\bar{1} - C_\tau(x_\alpha, r))$. And so by Theorem 3.9 (ii), $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq (\bar{1} - C_\tau(x_\alpha, r))$ because $(\bar{1} - C_\tau(x_\alpha, r))$ is r -frso set in X . Which implies that $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq (\bar{1} - C_\tau(x_\alpha, r))$. Hence by Lemma 2.8, $\lceil x_\alpha q C_\tau^*(\lambda, r)$. Therefore $x_\alpha q C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \Rightarrow C_\tau(x_\alpha, r)q\lambda$ for any fuzzy point x_α of X .

Theorem 3.11. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$. A fuzzy set λ is r -fuzzy*-dense in itself and r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set, then λ is r -fuzzy rw -closed.

PROOF. Let μ be a r -frso set of X such that $\lambda \leq \mu$. Then by Theorem 3.9 (ii), $C_\tau^*(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$. Therefore, $C_\tau(\lambda, r) \leq \mu$, because λ is r -fuzzy*-dense in itself. Hence λ is r -fuzzy rw -closed.

Theorem 3.12. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in I^X, r \in I_0$. If λ_1 and λ_2 are r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed sets, then $\lambda_1 \vee \lambda_2$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

PROOF. Let μ be a r -frso set of X such that $\lambda_1 \vee \lambda_2 \leq \mu$. Then $\lambda_1 \leq \mu$ and $\lambda_2 \leq \mu$. Therefore $\lambda_1^* \leq \mu$ and $\lambda_2^* \leq \mu$ because λ_1 and λ_2 are r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed sets of X . Hence $(\lambda_1 \vee \lambda_2)^* \leq \mu$ and $\lambda_1 \vee \lambda_2$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

Remark 3.13. The intersection of two r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed sets in a fits (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) may not be r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

Example 3.14. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta_1, \delta_2 \in I^X, r \in I_0$ are defined as follows: $\alpha(a) = 1, \alpha(b) = 0, \alpha(c) = 0, \alpha(d) = 0; \beta(a) = 0, \beta(b) = 1, \beta(c) = 0, \beta(d) = 0; \gamma(a) = 1, \gamma(b) = 1, \gamma(c) = 0, \gamma(d) = 0; \delta_1(a) = 1, \delta_1(b) = 0, \delta_1(c) = 1, \delta_1(d) = 1; \delta_2(a) = 1, \delta_2(b) = 1, \delta_2(c) = 1, \delta_2(d) = 0; \lambda(a) = 1, \lambda(b) = 0, \lambda(c) = 1, \lambda(d) = 0$. We define fuzzy topology $\tau : I^X \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \alpha, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \beta, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \gamma, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

If we take $\mathcal{I} = \{0_X\}$, the fuzzy sets δ_1 and δ_2 are r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed sets in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) . Then $\lambda = \delta_1 \wedge \delta_2$ is not r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

Theorem 3.15. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in I^X, r \in I_0$ such that $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq C_\tau^*(\lambda_1, r)$. If λ_1 is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set in X , then λ_2 is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

PROOF. Let μ be a r -frso set such that $\lambda_2 \leq \mu$. Since $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2$ we have $\lambda_1 \leq \mu$. Hence, $C_\tau^*(\lambda_1, r) \leq \mu$ because λ_1 is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed. Now $\lambda_2 \leq C_\tau^*(\lambda_1, r)$ implies that $C_\tau^*(\lambda_2, r) \leq C_\tau^*(\lambda_1, r) \leq \mu$. Consequently λ_2 is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

Theorem 3.16. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits and for any $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in I^X, r \in I_0$ such that $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \lambda_1^*$. Then λ_1 and λ_2 are r -fuzzy rw -closed.

PROOF. Obvious.

Theorem 3.17. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in I^X, r \in I_0$. If λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy subsets of X such that $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \lambda_1^*$ and λ_1 is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed. Then $\lambda_1^* \leq \lambda_2^*$ and λ_2 is r -fuzzy*-open.

PROOF. Obvious.

Definition 3.18. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$. A fuzzy set λ is called r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open if its complement $\bar{1} - \lambda$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed.

Remark 3.19. Every r -fuzzy rw -open (resp. r -fuzzy $*$ -open) set is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open. But the converse may not be true.

Theorem 3.20. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits and $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$. Then λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open if and only if $\delta \leq I_{\tau}^*(\lambda, r)$ whenever δ is a r -frsc and $\delta \leq \lambda$.

PROOF. Necessity: Let λ be r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open and δ is a r -frsc set such that $\delta \leq \lambda$. Then $\bar{1} - \lambda$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed, $\bar{1} - \lambda \leq \bar{1} - \delta$ and $\bar{1} - \delta$ is a r -frso in X . Hence $C_{\tau}^*(\bar{1} - \lambda, r) \leq \bar{1} - \delta$. Which implies that $\delta \leq I_{\tau}^*(\lambda)$. Sufficiency: Let μ be a r -frso set such that $\bar{1} - \lambda \leq \mu$. Then $\bar{1} - \mu$ is r -frsc set of X such that $\bar{1} - \mu \leq \lambda$. And so by hypothesis, $\bar{1} - \mu \leq I_{\tau}^*(\lambda, r)$. Which implies that $C_{\tau}^*(\bar{1} - \lambda, r) \leq \mu$ and $\bar{1} - \lambda$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed. Hence λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open.

Theorem 3.21. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits, $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$. If λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open and $I_{\tau}^*(\lambda, r) \leq \lambda_2 \leq \lambda_1$, then λ_2 is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open.

PROOF. Follows from Definition 3.18 and Theorem 3.15.

4. Fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous mappings

Definition 4.1. A mapping $f : (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be

- (1) fuzzy rw -continuous if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy rw -closed in X , for every $\lambda \in I^Y, r \in I_0$ with $\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda) \geq r$.
- (2) fuzzy I_w -continuous if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_w -closed in X , for every $\lambda \in I^Y, r \in I_0$ with $\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda) \geq r$.
- (3) fuzzy I_{rg} -continuous if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rg} -closed in X , for every $\lambda \in I^Y, r \in I_0$ with $\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda) \geq r$.
- (4) fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in X , for every $\lambda \in I^Y, r \in I_0$ with $\tau(\bar{1} - \lambda) \geq r$.

Theorem 4.2. A mapping $f : (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous if and only if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open in X , for every $\lambda \in I^Y, r \in I_0$ with $\tau(\lambda) \geq r$.

PROOF. It is obvious because $f^{-1}(\bar{1} - \lambda) = \bar{1} - f^{-1}(\lambda)$ for every $\lambda \in I^Y$.

- Remark 4.3.*
- (i) Every fuzzy I_w -continuous mapping is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous, but the converse is not true.
 - (ii) Every fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous mapping is fuzzy I_{rg} -continuous, but the converse is not true.
 - (iii) Every fuzzy rw -continuous mapping is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous, but the converse is not true.

Example 4.4. Let $X = \{a, b\}, Y = \{p, q\}, \lambda \in I^X$ and $\mu \in I^Y$ are defined as follows: $\lambda(a) = 0.7, \lambda(b) = 0.6; \mu(p) = 0.4, \mu(q) = 0.3$. We define fuzzy topologies $\tau, \sigma : I^X \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \lambda, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \sigma(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \mu, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\tau = \{0, 1, \lambda\}, \sigma = \{0, 1, \mu\}$ be the fuzzy topology on X and Y respectively and $I = \{0_X\}$ be the fuzzy ideal on X . Then the mapping $f : (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ defined by $f(a) = p$ and $f(b) = q$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous but it is not fuzzy I_w -continuous, as the inverse image of closed set μ^c in Y is not fuzzy I_w -closed set in X .

Example 4.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $Y = \{p, q, r, s\}$, the fuzzy sets $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in I^X$ and $\lambda \in I^Y$ are defined as follows: $\alpha(a) = 0.4, \alpha(b) = 0.3, \alpha(c) = 0.5, \alpha(d) = 0.3; \beta(a) = 0.3, \beta(b) = 0.5, \beta(c) = 0.3, \beta(d) = 0.4; \gamma(a) = 0.4, \gamma(b) = 0.5, \gamma(c) = 0.5, \gamma(d) = 0.4; \delta(a) = 0.3, \delta(b) = 0.3, \delta(c) = 0.3, \delta(d) = 0.3; \lambda(p) = 0.4, \lambda(q) = 0.5, \lambda(r) = 0.5, \lambda(s) = 0.5$. We define fuzzy topologies $\tau, \sigma : I^X, I^Y \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \alpha, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \beta, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \gamma, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \delta, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \sigma(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \lambda, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\mathcal{I} = \{0_X\}$ be the fuzzy ideal on X . Then the mapping $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ defined by $f(a) = p, f(b) = q, f(c) = r$ and $f(d) = s$ is fuzzy I_{rg} -continuous but it is not fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous, since $f^{-1}(\bar{1} - \lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rg} -closed but not r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set in X for every $\bar{1} - \lambda \in I^Y, r \in I_0$ with $\sigma(\bar{1} - \lambda) \geq r$.

Example 4.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $Y = \{p, q, r, s\}$, the fuzzy sets $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in I^X$ and $\lambda \in I^Y$ are defined as follows: $\alpha(a) = 0.5, \alpha(b) = 0.4, \alpha(c) = 0.6, \alpha(d) = 0.4; \beta(a) = 0.4, \beta(b) = 0.6, \beta(c) = 0.4, \beta(d) = 0.5; \gamma(a) = 0.5, \gamma(b) = 0.6, \gamma(c) = 0.6, \gamma(d) = 0.5; \delta(a) = 0.4, \delta(b) = 0.4, \delta(c) = 0.4, \delta(d) = 0.4; \lambda(p) = 0.5, \lambda(q) = 0.6, \lambda(r) = 0.4, \lambda(s) = 0.5$. We define fuzzy topologies $\tau, \sigma : I^X, I^Y \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \alpha, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \beta, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \gamma, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \delta, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \sigma(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \lambda, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\mathcal{I} = I^X$ be the fuzzy ideal on X . Then the mapping $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ defined by $f(a) = p, f(b) = q, f(c) = r$ and $f(d) = s$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous but it is not fuzzy rw -continuous, since $f^{-1}(\bar{1} - \lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed but not r -fuzzy rw -closed set in X for every $\bar{1} - \lambda \in I^Y, r \in I_0$ with $\sigma(\bar{1} - \lambda) \geq r$.

We have the following diagram using Diagram I and Theorem 4.2 and Remark 4.3.

Diagram -II

Theorem 4.7. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous then for each fuzzy point x_β of X and each r -fo set μ of Y such that $f(x_\beta) \in \mu$ then there exists a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set λ of X such that $x_\beta \in \lambda$ and $f(\lambda) \leq \mu$.

PROOF. Let x_β be a fuzzy point of X and μ is r -fo set of Y such that $f(x_\beta) \in \mu$, put $\lambda = f^{-1}(\mu)$. Then by hypothesis λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set of X such that $x_\beta \in \lambda$ and $f(\lambda) = f(f^{-1}(\mu)) \leq \mu$.

Theorem 4.8. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous then for each fuzzy point x_β of X and each r -fo set μ of Y such that $f(x_\beta)q\mu$ then there exists a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set λ of X such that $x_\beta q\lambda$ and $f(\lambda) \leq \mu$.

PROOF. Let x_β be a fuzzy point of X and μ is r -fo set of Y such that $f(x_\beta)q\mu$. Put $\lambda = f^{-1}(\mu)$. Then by hypothesis λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set of X such that $x_\beta q\lambda$ and $f(\lambda) = f(f^{-1}(\mu)) \leq \mu$.

Definition 4.9. Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be a fits. The fuzzy I_{rw} -closure of a fuzzy set λ of X denoted by $I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(\lambda, r)$ is defined as:

$$I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(\lambda, r) = \bigwedge \{ \mu \in I^X : \lambda \leq \mu, \mu \text{ is } r\text{-fuzzy } I_{rw} \text{-closed set} \}.$$

Remark 4.10. It is clear that $\lambda \leq I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(\lambda, r) \leq C_\tau(\lambda, r)$ for any $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$.

Theorem 4.11. A mapping $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous then $f(I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(\lambda)) \leq C_\tau(f(\lambda, r))$ for every $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I^X$.

PROOF. Let $\lambda \in I^X, r \in I_0$. Then $C_\tau(f(\lambda, r))$ is a r -fc set of Y . Since f is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous, $f^{-1}(C_\tau(f(\lambda, r)))$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in X . Clearly, $\lambda \leq f^{-1}(C_\tau(f(\lambda, r)))$. Therefore $I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(\lambda, r) \leq I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(f^{-1}(C_\tau(f(\lambda, r)))) = f^{-1}(C_\tau(f(\lambda, r)))$. Hence $f(I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(\lambda, r)) \leq C_\tau(f(\lambda, r))$.

Remark 4.12. The converse of above Theorem may not be true. For,

Example 4.13. In Example 4.5, $f(I_{rw}\text{-}C_\tau(\lambda, r)) \leq C_\tau(f(\lambda), r)$ holds for every fuzzy set $\lambda \in I^X$, but it is not fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

Definition 4.14. A fits (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) is r -fuzzy $I_{rw}\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space if every r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set is r -fc set.

Theorem 4.15. A mapping f from a fuzzy $I_{rw}\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) to a fuzzy topological space (Y, σ) is fuzzy continuous if and only if it is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

PROOF. Suppose the function $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is fuzzy continuous. Let λ be r -fc set in Y . Then $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fc set in X . Since every r -fuzzy closed set is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed. And therefore $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set in X . Hence f is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

Conversely, assume that $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous. Let λ be a r -fuzzy closed set in Y . Then $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set in X . By assumption (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) is r -fuzzy $I_{rw}\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space which implies that $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy closed set in X . Hence f is fuzzy continuous.

Remark 4.16. The composition of two fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous mappings may not be fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous. For,

Example 4.17. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}, Y = \{x, y, z\}$ and $Z = \{p, q, r\}$ and the fuzzy sets $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in I^X, \delta_1 \in I^Y, \delta_2 \in I^Z$ are defined as follows: $\alpha(a) = 1, \alpha(b) = 0, \alpha(c) = 0; \beta(a) = 0, \beta(b) = 1, \beta(c) = 0; \gamma(a) = 1, \gamma(b) = 1, \gamma(c) = 0; \delta_1(x) = 1, \delta_1(y) = 1, \delta_1(z) = 0; \delta_2(p) = 1, \delta_2(q) = 0, \delta_2(r) = 1$. We define fuzzy topologies $\tau, \sigma, \eta : I^X \rightarrow I$ as follows:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \alpha, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \beta, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \gamma, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \sigma(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \delta_1, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \eta(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda \in \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \lambda = \delta_2, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\mathcal{I} = \{0_X\}$ be the fuzzy ideal on X and Y . Then the mapping $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ defined by $f(a) = x, f(b) = y, f(c) = z$ and the mapping $g : (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ defined by $g(x) = p, g(y) = q, g(z) = r$ are fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous but gof is not fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

Theorem 4.18. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy continuous. Then $gof : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

PROOF. Let λ be a r -fc in Z then $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fc in Y , because g is fuzzy continuous. Therefore $(gof)^{-1}(\lambda) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(\lambda))$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in X . Hence gof is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

Theorem 4.19. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy continuous and (Y, σ) is r -fuzzy I_{rw} - $T_{1/2}$ space, then $gof : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

PROOF. Let λ be a r -fc set in Z then $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fc set in Y because g is fuzzy continuous. Since Y is r -fuzzy I_{rw} - $T_{1/2}$ space, $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy closed in Y . And so, $(gof)^{-1}(\lambda) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(\lambda))$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in X . Hence $gof : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

Theorem 4.20. If mappings $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous and fuzzy I_{rw} - $T_{1/2}$ space then $gof : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

PROOF. Obvious.

5. Fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute mappings

Definition 5.1. A mapping $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ is said to be fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in X , for every r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set λ of Y .

Theorem 5.2. A mapping $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute if and only if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open in X , for every r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set λ of Y .

PROOF. It is obvious because $f^{-1}(\bar{1} - \lambda) = \bar{1} - f^{-1}(\lambda)$ for every fuzzy set λ of Y .

Theorem 5.3. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ and $g : (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta, \mathcal{I})$ are both fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute, then $g \circ f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta, \mathcal{I})$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute.

PROOF. Let γ be a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed set in (Z, η, \mathcal{I}) . Since g is a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute, $g^{-1}(\gamma)$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in (Y, σ, \mathcal{I}) . As f is fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(\gamma))$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) . Thus $(g \circ f)^{-1}(\gamma) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(\gamma))$ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -closed in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) and $(g \circ f)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute.

Theorem 5.4. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute and $g : (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous then their composition $g \circ f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -continuous.

PROOF. Follows from Definitions 4.1 and 5.1.

Theorem 5.5. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute then for each fuzzy point x_β of X and each r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set μ of Y such that $f(x_\beta) \in \mu$ then there exists a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set λ of X such that $x_\beta \in \lambda$ and $f(\lambda) \leq \mu$.

PROOF. Let x_β be a fuzzy point of X and μ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set such that $f(x_\beta) \in \mu$, put $\lambda = f^{-1}(\mu)$. Then by hypothesis λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set of X such that $x_\beta \in \lambda$ and $f(\lambda) = f(f^{-1}(\mu)) \leq \mu$.

Theorem 5.6. If $f : (X, \tau, \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$ is fuzzy I_{rw} -irresolute then for each fuzzy point x_β of X and each r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set μ of Y such that $f(x_\beta)q\mu$ then there exists a r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set λ of X such that $x_\beta q\lambda$ and $f(\lambda) \leq \mu$.

PROOF. Let x_β be a fuzzy point of X and μ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set such that $f(x_\beta)q\mu$. Put $\lambda = f^{-1}(\mu)$. Then by hypothesis λ is r -fuzzy I_{rw} -open set of X such that $x_\beta q\lambda$ and $f(\lambda) = f(f^{-1}(\mu)) \leq \mu$.

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